

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECTS OF FAMILY CLIMATE ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

This study investigated the impact of family climate on the academic achievement of government and private secondary school students. Three hundred (Boys =150; Girls =150) secondary school students were randomly chosen as the sample of the study from 8 schools (4 government and 4 private) of Aligarh. Family Climate Scale by Dr. Beena Shah (1990) was used to study respondent's family climate, while their IX class examination results were used as the measure of academic achievement. The hypotheses were tested using the product moment coefficient of correlation to find out the relationship between the family climate and academic achievement, and for measuring the effect of the type of family climate (favorable and unfavorable) on the academic achievement of the students the investigator applied t-test. The results showed that the academic achievements of students are independent of the family environment and parental support provided to them. The study also revealed that private students have good academic records in comparison of government students.

Keywords:

Family, Family Climate, Achievement, Academic Achievement, Secondary School Students

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1. INTRODUCTION

It is an accepted fact that the growth and development of a nation depends upon the quality of human resources, which in turn depends upon the quality of education, which is further influenced by the favorable and unfavorable family climate. Family Climate exerts a deep and persistent influence on the life of the individual, for it is the family in which he acquires the intimate experiences. Thus the child comes to the school not as an independent and individualized being, but as a little, undivided part of the family, and it is in fact with the family that the school copes, rather than with the child as an individual.

Family: The family is a group consisting of parents and children, and is the oldest, basic and fundamental unit of human society. The earliest functions of this most ancient and revered social

institution were to beget children; to supply food, shelter, and protection to offspring; to prepare the child for adult pursuits; and to transmit the accumulated social heritage to children. Burgess and Locke (1963) have defined family as “a group of persons united by the ties of marriage, blood or adoption constituting a single household interacting and intercommunication with each other in their respective social role of husband and wife, mother and father, son and daughter, brother and sister creating and maintaining a common culture”.

Family Climate: Family being the first and major agency of socialization has great influence and bearing on the development of the child. The word “Climate” is a more comprehensive one. It includes within itself the word “Environment”. The human elements surrounding the child constitute the “Environment”. It embraces the social, physical and emotional activities of the family. All these combined together constitute the “Family Climate” [Manual FCS Beena Shah 1990]. Parveen, A. (2007) made an attempt to examine the effect of home environment on personality and academic achievement of senior secondary students. And results revealed that home environment significantly affects academic achievement of students. It was found that students who belonged to good home environment group had highest mean achievement score and while lowest mean achievement score was found for students who belonged to poor home environment group.

Achievement: Achievement is a term used to indicate the degree of success attained in some general or specific area. It represents the acquirements of knowledge and skill and may employ the ability to make appropriate use of such knowledge or skill in a variety of present and future situations. The dictionary of education by C.V Good (1973) defines achievement as “accomplishment or proficiency of performance in a given skill or body of knowledge”.

Academic Achievement: Educators tend to use the term “academic achievement” in relation to attained ability in the school subjects, although this is a restricted use of the term which may be applied to the entire endeavor. Academic achievement plays an important role in one’s life because it pushes an individual towards his goal. It enables him to choose his vocation in this modern age of competition. It has also been noticed that individuals who perform academically higher also attain a high status in the society. Moos, R.H & Moos, B.S (1986) indicated that family environment may be independence oriented, achievement oriented, moral-religious oriented, intellectual cultural oriented, support oriented, conflict oriented and disorganized families. All these have significant influence on the behavior, development and social competence of child. This is more or less a hidden curriculum that transmits a pattern of development through parent-child and child-child interaction in any culture.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives were formulated for the study:

- I. To find out the relationship between the family climate and the academic achievement of secondary school students.
- II. To find out the difference between male and female students belonging to favorable family climate with respect to their academic achievement.
- III. To find out the difference between male and female students belonging to unfavorable family climate with respect to their academic achievement.
- IV. To investigate the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government secondary school students belonging to favorable family climate.
- V. To investigate the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government secondary school students belonging to unfavorable family climate.
- VI. To find out the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to favorable family climate.
- VII. To find out the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to unfavorable family climate.
- VIII. To find out the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to favorable family climate.
- IX. To find out the difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

3. HYPOTHESES

Corresponding to the objectives of the present study, the hypotheses are:

- I. There exists no significant correlation between the family climate and the academic achievements of the students.
- II. There exists no significant difference between male and female students belonging to favorable family climate with respect to their academic achievement.
- III. There exists no significant difference between male and female students belonging to unfavorable family climate with respect to their academic achievement.
- IV. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of the private and government secondary school students belonging to favorable family climate.
- V. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of the private and government secondary school students belonging to unfavorable family climate.
- VI. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to favorable family climate.
- VII. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to unfavorable family climate.
- VIII. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to favorable family climate.
- IX. There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

4. DELIMITATIONS

Delimitations of the present study are:

- I. Sample consists of students belonging to government and private secondary schools of Aligarh district only. Therefore findings of this study should not be generalized to any other district/state of India or any other level of education such as elementary or higher education.
- II. Academic achievements of students may be affected by many factors but only family climate is studied under the present investigation.
- III. In the present study, only correlation and t-test are applied.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1.SAMPLE

In the present study, the sample consisted of 300 students of X class selected from 8 schools. Out of 8 schools, 4 schools were government, and 4 were private. Random sampling technique has been employed to select the sample.

5.2.TOOLS USED

In the present study, investigator chose Family Climate Scale prepared by Dr. Beena Shah for measuring family climate of secondary school students. And for gauging the academic achievement the data were collected from school records. The marks of final examination of IX class were taken as index of academic achievement. Variations were found in the grand total of different schools, so the marks were converted on a common scale i.e. out of 1000.

5.3.STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Keeping in view the natures of the data the investigator used **Mean** as the measure of central tendency. And to measure spread or dispersion of scores in the distribution investigator made use of **Standard Deviation**. To find out the relationship between the family climate and academic achievement, the investigator used the **Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation**. For measuring the effect of the type of family climate (favorable and unfavorable) on the academic achievement of the students the investigator applied **t-test**.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1: There exists no significant correlation between the family climate and the academic achievements of the students.

Table 1: Correlation between family climate and academic achievement

N	$\sum x$	$\sum y$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	Correlation
300	33839	164975	3892443	95328883	18703440	0.161 insignificant

Table 1 indicates that if we take an overall view of correlation between family climate and academic achievements of secondary school students then $\sum x = 33839$ and $\sum y = 164975$, and correlation obtained is $r = .161$, which means there is no or almost negligible relationship between these two variables.

Hypothesis 2: There exists no significant difference between male and female students belonging to favorable family climate group on the measures of academic achievement.

Table 2: Academic achievement scores of male and female students of favorable family climate group

Favourable Family Climate Group	N	Academic Achievement Scores Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Male	76	578	128.7	144	0.359 insignificant
Female	70	571	110		

Table 2 shows that the calculated 't' value is insignificant both at 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus the academic achievement of male and female students is independent of favorable family climate effects.

Hypothesis 3: There exists no significant difference between male and female students belonging to unfavorable family climate on the measures of academic achievement.

Table 3: Academic achievement scores of male and female students of unfavorable family climate.

Unfavourable Family Climate Group	N	Academic Achievement Scores Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Male	74	525	146	152	0.193 Insignificant
Female	80	521	112		

The calculated 't' value is insignificant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. The mean scores of both male and female are in the range of 521-525. Thus the null hypothesis that there will be no significant

difference in academic achievement scores of male and female students of favorable family climate is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There exists no significant difference between the achievement scores of the private and government secondary school students belonging to favorable family climate group.

Table 4: Academic achievement scores of government and private school students belonging to favorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Scores Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	68	597	100	144	2.174 Significant
Government	78	555	132		

Calculated 't' value is 2.174, indicates that a significant difference exists at 0.05 level. The mean score of private schools is higher than government school mean. Thus, the null hypothesis that there will be no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of government and private school students belonging to favorable family climate is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: There exists no significant difference between the achievement scores of the private and government secondary school students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

Table 5: Academic achievement scores of government and private school students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	82	546	105.4	152	2.290 Significant
Government	72	501	137.9		

Calculated 't' value is 2.290, it indicates that a significant difference exists at 0.05 level. The mean score of private schools students is higher than the mean scores of the government school students. Thus, the null hypothesis that there will be no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of government and private school students belonging to unfavorable family climate is rejected.

Hypothesis 6: There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to favorable family climate.

Table 6: Academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to favorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	35	570	87	74	0.478
Government	41	585	156.6		Insignificant

Calculated 't' value 0.478 is insignificant at 0.05 level. Thus the null hypothesis that there will be no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to favorable family climate group is accepted

Hypothesis 7: There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to unfavorable family climate

Table 7: Academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	40	507.9	130.2	72	1.107
Government	34	545.5	162.4		Insignificant

Calculated 't' value is 1.107 which is insignificant at 0.05 level. The mean score of government school male students is greater than private school students, but this difference is insignificant. Thus the null hypothesis that there will be no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government male students belonging to unfavorable family climate is accepted.

Hypothesis 8: There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to favorable family climate.

Table 8: Academic achievement scores of government and private female students belonging to favorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	33	626.5	106.4		4.470

Government	37	522	89.101	68	Significant
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Calculated 't' value is 4.470 is significant at 0.05 level. The mean score of private schools is higher than government schools. It indicates that significant difference exist between the academic scores of female private and government school students. Thus the null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to favorable family climate group is rejected.

Hypothesis 9: There exists no significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

Table 9: Academic achievement scores of government and private female students belonging to unfavorable family climate.

Type of School	N	Academic Achievement Mean	S.D	d.f	t
Private	42	574	98.7	78	5.090 Significant
Government	38	462.2	97.98		

Calculated 't' value 5.090 is significant at 0.05 level. The mean of private schools students is greater than government school female students. It indicates that there exists significant difference between the academic achievement scores of private and government female students belonging to unfavorable family climate. Thus the hypothesis 9 is rejected

7. CONCLUSIONS

As we have found from our findings that no significant relationship exists between family climate and academic achievement of secondary school students. It is noticed that, male and female students belonging to same family climate either favorable or unfavorable did not show any statistical differences in their academic performances. However the mean score of male students is slight higher than female students. This difference in mean is insignificant and it depicts that family climate exerts uniform effect on students, whether male or female. In the present study female students are more prone to unfavorable family climate in comparison to male students. Thus, it is evident that boys receive more attention and guidance at home in comparison to girls. It has been noticed that private students have good academic records in comparison of government students

8. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Findings of this study have some important implications in the field of education. In the light of findings of this study, some important suggestions related to education are as follows:

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1. Schools should provide maximum facilities to their students in terms of infrastructure and quality education. To a certain extent private schools are successful in providing all these facilities whereas government schools are far behind in the provision of these facilities.
2. Solution of this wide disparity between government and private school education lie in 'quality education'. Quality education consists clearer understanding by the teachers of what competencies are to be developed among the students, the class-room practices that bring out the best among the children in the most non-threatening and exciting manner, the competitive spirit that the school is able to create, the parents' untiring interest in their children's learning, and the pressures created by an active and lively parent-teacher interaction for better delivery of learning in the school.
3. Schools and families share a common objective which is the education of new generation and its preparation for a better member of the society. Parents are considered to be a child's first teacher while teachers as their second parents. Therefore, if one institution i.e. family fails to deliver its responsibilities sincerely, then it becomes the major responsibility of other institution i.e. school to help them to achieve maximum success in life. And the negative impact of family environment can thus be minimized.
4. Women in India continue to be denied of their rights throughout the education cycle, and still face huge discrimination and disadvantages in terms of access, progress, learning and their experiences in schools. Boys are depicted as strong, adventurous and intelligent whereas females as weak. Thus they get more favors at the homes in comparison to girls. And this in reverse affects the academic scores of female students. Gender discrimination cannot be eradicated unless there is camaraderie, dignity and partnership among the members of family and within the social environment. (The Hindu-Dec-18, 2001).
5. Government schools should be made accountable to parents and neighborhood instead of bureaucrats. Efforts should be made for the autonomy of schools. And teachers should be made responsible to parents. And parents should come forward and get involved in school association. In America, the best schools in communities are those, where parents are involved and PTAs (parent-teacher associations) are established.
6. It is needless to emphasize that the school and the parents must take keen interest in the education of the children. Teachers should encourage parents to be aware of school policies and the curriculum. And letting them know about the best way to communicate with their teens and help them in their studies. Such strategies will foster positive climate and make parents more involved and responsive in school's activities. Thus, schools should try to achieve maximum level of excellence, and both private and government schools should try to compete on equal grounds.

Thus, education is the foundation upon which we have to build our society. It is an investment which has the biggest multiplier. Therefore it has to be our first social priority.

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